

Effects of Employee Training on Organisational Commitment: Exploring Human Resource Development Programmes in Nigerian University

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Abstract

This paper assessed the effects of employee training on organizational commitment: exploring human resource development programmes in Nigerian Universities. The study adopted a survey research method. The target population consists of seventy- four (74) senior administrative and academic staff of University of Nigeria. The study sought to examine the effect of training on – the- job on employee commitment, moreso, examine the effect of training off- the- job on organizational commitment and examine the decision-making skills required for executive development. The sampled data were tested by ordinal logistic regression technique. The results revealed that training on–the - the job has a positive effect on employee commitment: This indicates that employee performance and commitment increase when a newly employed person receives guidance and counseling from a superior in the organization. Consequently, training-off–the–job has a positive effect on organizational commitment: Training-off- the- job involves any form of training that takes place outside the work premises. The trainee focuses on learning the job. However, in–basket–training programme and case studies training programme are decision-making skills required for executive development. This study has implication on human resource development, career development, and organizational effectiveness. There have been previous works done on the effects of training on organizational commitment, but there has been rarely previous work done on this topic for investigation. Therefore, a research gap exists which can be purposely filled by this study. However, the study suggested that there should be a clear commitment to training throughout all levels of the organization. Top management should set the scene by giving active support and encouragement to the training process, and through the provision of adequate finance, resources, time and skilled staff.

Keywords: Training, Development, Human Resource capital, and Organisational Commitment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current business scenario appears to be characterized by high competitiveness among organizations, market globalization, and technological advancement. To survive in such challenging situations, organizations have to look for the possible ways to create sustainable competitive advantages. In this context, the knowledge and skills of employees in an organization have increasingly become very essential to its performance, global competitiveness, and continuous development (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). Training is one of the main strategies to achieve organizational goals by attracting and retaining employees, and also to effectively manage them. This result provides practical implication for the decision makers in higher educational institutions to focus on providing training programmes for their employees to ensure that they have enough skills and knowledge to perform their duties efficiently (Vasudevan, 2014). Training and development boost employees' knowledge base and skills required to perform their jobs effectively and efficiently, take on new responsibilities, as well as adapt to changing conditions. Training plays a crucial role in teaching employees on how to perform their responsibilities as well as enable them to acquire the requisite knowledge and skills for effective performance. Basically, development is concerned with improving the knowledge and skills of employees such that they can tackle new challenges and responsibilities. Training tends to be used more frequently at lower levels of an organization: development tends to be used more frequently with professionals and managers. Before creating training and development programmes, managers should perform a need assessment in which they determine which employees need training or development and what type of skill or knowledge they need to acquire. When organizations undergo major changes, training and development activities often are necessary to help employees make the transition to a new way of doing things. Redesigning work around teams is one type of change that

creates high demand for training and development (Hellriegel, Jackson, and Slocum, 1999). Development is necessary and a prerequisite for the individual, organizations, and the society. Magginson, Mosley, and Pictri (1986) suggest that training is attaining specific detailed and routine job skills and techniques. Development is the broader scope of improvement and growth of abilities, attitudes, and personality trait. Development is required to meet technological advances and to achieve greater personal satisfaction. People become developed when they have acquired the necessary education and training that could enable them exhibit growth in abilities, attitudes, and personality trait. As people become developed, they have a greater sense of dignity and worth which will make them be more valuable to their employers and the society in general.

Becker, (1993) posits that it is acknowledged both in theory and in practice that training is not only related to employee job performance but also to employees' attitudes toward their work and organization. Therefore, training involves teaching oneself or/and others any skill and knowledge that relate to specific useful competencies. In other words, training has a specific goal of improving employees' capacity, capability, productivity, and performance. Generally, it acts as a framework for apprenticeships and provides the backbone of content at technology and educational institutions. As succinctly put by (Scott and Meyer, 1991) training can be viewed as a management practice that can be controlled or managed to elicit a desired set of unwritten, reciprocal attitudes and behavior, including job involvement, motivation, and organizational commitment. Similarly, Armstrong (2001) states that the objectives of employee training in organisations are development of employee competency and improvement of their performances, employee growth within the organisation, such that future human resource needs of the organisation can be met and lastly reduction of employee learning time in the case of new appointments, transfer or promotion. Tomer (2001) posits that training does not only enhance skills and capabilities but also improves employee satisfaction within the workplace. Increased satisfaction in the workplace is assumed to enhance organizational commitment. Bulut and Culha, (2010) state that organizational training is positively linked to enhanced employee attitudes and organizational commitment. Training is required to acquire and improve skills of employees in an organization. Employees need to be trained and retrained so as to meet up with the changing environmental demands. Organisations that operate in a stable environment rarely train their workers to update their skills: This could be due to the bureaucratic system of such organizations. Employee requires training to start a new job and training is also required to update skills so as to prevent skill obsolescence. Some organizations do not train their workers because of the costs involved. Ahmad and Bakar (2003) posit that, despite the availability of training programmes, there is still concern over the contribution of training to the desired organizational outcomes, such as commitment. The effect of training on commitment has received less attention than it deserves. In spite of the increase in training expenditure, employers are highly concerned about the significant risks of losing well – trained employees to competitors and potentially wasting large sums of corporate monies (Mello, 2011).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1: Organisational Commitment and Drivers of Organisational Performance

In the current and dynamic business environments, various organizations make a significant sacrifice to ensure organizational commitment and job satisfaction among their employees for the purpose of maintaining them and improving their productivity. Organisational commitment has been widely accepted to be beneficial for both the organization and its employees as it can reinforce the feeling of belongingness, security of the job, career development, improved compensation and higher intrinsic rewards. Consequently, Latham (1990) succinctly put that highly committed and loyal employees are essential in order to achieve organizational goals. More so, employees with strong organizational commitment will likely develop an emotional relation to their organizations and feel happy with greater intention to make important contributions (Hanaysha, 2016). Thus, Ghorbanhosseini (2012) posits that organizational commitment refers to the loyalty of an employee towards his or her organization while (Meyer & Allen, 1997) described it as the degree of attachment to an organization which is characterized by valuing the shared benefits held between an employee and his or her organization.

Deductively, a committed employee is one who is punctual, puts in overtime, protect company assets, shares her goals as well as one who will stay with the organization through difficulties. Moreover, organizational commitment is seen by Rae (2013) as a desire to maintain the affiliation with an organization and is reflected in the willingness to exert a high level of effort, to achieve organizational goals. The following factors were found by Luthans and Doh (2012) to be strong drivers of employee commitment/and performance. Management Effectiveness: employees are motivated when their managers have the sound decision-making ability, successfully engage their employees, and value their employees.

Positive Work Environment: to be productive, employees need a healthy, safe workplace with access to information needed to do their jobs.

Clear communication: managers can increase commitment by making sure employees understand their company's goals, their own job, and the link between their job and the customer.

Evidently, having employees utilize self-direction and self-control in pursuit of common objectives were far more beneficial to imposing a system of controls which forces them to pursue objectives they didn't understand. Hence, rewarding people for achievement was a far more effective way to reinforce shared commitment than punishing them for failure.

Basically, employees' commitment is very important for sustained organizational success, thus, extrinsic and intrinsic rewards should be made adequate to the employees as well as clear communication, healthy work environment, and management efficiency.

Organisational performance is the ability of an organization to efficiently utilize its resources to obtain outputs that are consistent with its goals and objectives and also relevant for its clients and stakeholders. Organisational performance involves the real output or results of an organization as measured against its goals and objectives and intended outputs (Ezigbo, 2011).

2.2: Training - on – the- Job

Training -on – the- job involves employee training at the workplace while he or she is doing the actual job. He is subjected to close and intensive supervision. The trainee acquires the skill and knowledge which his new job requires through practice and observation. Usually, a professional trainer (sometimes an experienced employee) serves as the course instructor. Training-on-the-job could be in the form of coaching, understudy, job rotation and performance appraisal. Coaching involves superiors providing guidance and counseling to subordinates in the course of their regular job performance. Here experienced employee advice and guides trainees in solving work problems. Understudy involves employee working as a subordinate partner with a boss so that eventually the personnel can assume the full responsibilities and duties of the particular job. Job rotation is designed to give a broad individual experience through exposure to many different areas of the organization. In this setup, within the organization, the trainee moves from one job to another and generally remaining in each job cycle from six months to one year. Formal Performance Appraisal requires managers rating of each employee's performance in accordance with the predetermined performance criteria over a period of time (Ezigbo, 2011).

According to Becker, Bose and Freeman (2006) one way to develop and improve the quality of employee is to provide them with beneficial training and development programmes. This is because the capabilities, knowledge and skills of the talented employees were proved to be the key determinants of competitive advantage in global marketplaces. Similarly, Meyer and Allen (1997) posit that, to effectively develop such knowledge, skills and capabilities of employees to perform well, on- the- job training programmes are necessary in supporting the organizational members. As succinctly put by Truitt (2011) training is related with the skills that an employee should gain to help him or her work with others in order to achieve organizational goals and objectives. Past studies found that training – on- the – job has positive effect on employee commitment (Meyer and Allen (1997) and Truitt, 2011). Nkosi (2015) confirmed that training has a significant effect on employee commitment and overall retention. Based on the above discussion, this hypothesis is proposed. H1: Training on – the -job has positive effect on employee commitment.

2.3: Training- off- the- Job

Training-off-the-job involves any form of training that takes place outside the work premises. This implies that the employee does not count as a directly productive worker while such training takes place. Training off-the-job utilizes lectures, case studies, simulation, and executive development programmes at universities or other educational institutions. It has the advantage of allowing people to get away from work and concentrate more thoroughly on the training itself. This type of training has proven more effective in calculating concepts and ideas. Training off-the-job also involves vestibule training and apprenticeship training. Vestibule training takes place in a training area equipped with replica machines and tools outside the main office location. It is usually conducted by the organization's instructor or hired personnel. Vestibule training concentrates the attention of the trainee on learning the job only, unlike training on-the-job where the trainee does some productive work as he learns (Magginson, Mosley, and Pictri, 1986). As succinctly put by Ezigbo (2011) apprenticeship training provides an individual with the knowledge and skill in doing a craft or a series of the related job. The aim of apprenticeship programme is to develop higher skills among workers. Apprenticeship training programme tends to be mere general education than training on-the-job and vestibule school methods. Usually, apprenticeship programme combines training on-the-job and experience with classroom instruction in specific subjects. It is outside the work environment of organizations whereby a master of the craft imparts his knowledge, skill, and expertise to the individual apprentice. He, therefore, supervises the apprentice's activities and equally assigns projects to be executed by the apprentice. In this way, the apprentice learns by observation and imitation. Apprenticeship training is mostly employed in skilled trades, such as printing, arts, metal work, wood work, tailoring, carpentry work, retail trade, etc. Apprenticeship training could be for two, three, four, five, or seven years depending on the agreement reached. Apprenticeship training is required by an organization when the organization acquires a new technology. In this case, the organization can send one or two employees on apprenticeship training in the organization that has the new technology, to learn about the technology which their organization wants to adopt. Past studies found that Training off-the-job has a positive effect on organizational commitment. Buckley and Caple (2009) considered training as a systematic process that aims to help employees enhance their knowledge, skills, and develop positive behavior through a learning experience that is expected to help employees achieve greater performance. Similarly, Jun, Cai, and Shin (2006) posit that training provides various benefits to employees in terms of widening their knowledge, skills, and abilities, becoming more efficient team members, and improving career development. Based on the above discussion, this hypothesis is, therefore, proposed: H2: Training off-the-job has positive effect on organizational commitment.

2.4: Executive Development Programmes

Executive development is relevant as it is needed for the long run success of the organization through the acquisition of job skills, knowledge, insight, and attitudes to effectively manage the organization. Ezigbo (2011) suggests that executives mostly require decision-making skills, interpersonal skills, and general knowledge. Decision-making is a very important regular function of an executive. The training programmes that can be used in training an executive are in-basket training programme and Case studies. In-basket executive development programme provides information about the simulated company, its products, organization, key personnel, etc., to an executive trainee. The trainee executives are then provided with an in-basket of assorted memoranda, requests, letters on issues relating to the company's financial statements, marketing research information, petition from staff, letters of complaints from customers, replies of queries, etc. The trainee may be expected to prepare memos, react to issues concerning the organization, delegate tasks, and make decisions on the issues raised. Three types of executive abilities can be developed, such as situation judgment, in being able to recall details, establish priorities, and interrelate in terms. Social sensitivity in exhibiting courtesy in written notes, scheduling meeting, etc., and willingness to make a decision. In-basket-training helps the trainee to bring out innovative ideas that enhance decision making. Onwuchekwa (1995) posits that case studies provide the trainee with real-world case studies of companies. Usually, the cases would contain background information about the company, its products, finances, and organizational structure. The trainees are requested to diagnose and solve certain problems that are facing the companies mentioned in the cases. The aim of this exercise is

primarily at sharpening the trainee's ability to correctly identify the key problem in any given problem situation and in recommending the best solution for the given problem situation.

According to Ezigbo (2011), a manager needs to develop interpersonal competence so as to improve the level of the quality of his work. The types of executive training necessary to develop interpersonal skills are sensitivity training, transactional analysis, and structured insight. The aim of sensitivity training is to establish awareness and sensitivity to behavioral patterns of oneself and that of others with whom one relates. Sensitivity training is focused at making the trainees develop an increased openness to others, increased tolerance for individual differences, greater concern for others, less ethnic prejudice, understanding of group process, enhanced listening skills and increased support and trust.

Transactional analysis can be used to acquire interpersonal relationships. Here the emphasis is on understanding three ego states possessed by people. Berne (1950) cited by Ewurum (1998) demonstrated that people at times act like parents, at other times, like adults and at some other times, as children, thus analyzing interpersonal transactions in terms of these ego states: parent, adult, and child. The parent tends to be judgemental, condescending and punishing with frequent use of such words as, shouldn't, ought to and mustn't. The adult listens with an open mind, states opinion tentatively and actively engages in probability, estimating, and rational decision-making. The child is of two types: a free-spirited one of creativity and spontaneity, and also an adaptive and inhibited one that can be rebellious or overly submissive. Trainees are taught to analyze their interactions with others in terms of the ego states being expressed. It has been suggested that one who probably is low in the parent, high in adult and free child is likely to be most effective in dealing with others.

A manager, apart from his area of specialization, is expected to have general knowledge. The higher one goes up in the managerial hierarchy, the more he needs conceptual skills. The only way to improve on conceptual skill is to provide the executive with general knowledge through education. This educational knowledge can be provided through enrolling in educational institutions, special courses, selective reading, etc., (Onwuchekwa, 1995). Previous researchers see training as an essential activity for effective human resource management in any organization. The main principles of training stand on providing meaningful inputs for employees based on important theories, and to take into account the features of effectiveness and efficiency, differences among employees and continuous development (Diab and Ajlouni, 2015). Elnaga and Imran (2013) revealed that Employee training refers to programmes that aim to provide employees with required information, new skills to enhance the opportunities for professional development. Based on the earlier discussion, this hypothesis is presented: H₃: In-basket-training programme and case studies training programme are decision-making skills required for executive development

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted by using survey method and interview of employees at the University of Nigeria. The survey is usually associated with the deductive approach. It allows the collection of quantitative data which can be analyzed quantitatively using descriptive and inferential statistics. Secondary data were derived from books, journals, and internet. The target population consists of seventy-four (74) senior administrative and academic staff of the University which was purposely selected and considered suitable to be the sample. A quantitative approach was considered appropriate to use to ascertain the cause/ effect relationship between the variables. The sampled data were analyzed in tables, and the corresponding values expressed in percentages. Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) technique was used to test the hypotheses on SPSS (v.20). Opinions of experts from the academia were sought to ensure face and content validity.

Table 1: Analyses of Respondent's Responses

S/N	Questions	Yes, in Number	%	No, in Number	%	Total in Number	Total in %
1	<i>To ascertain the effect of training- on – the- job on employee commitment</i>						
(i)	Could manager's advice and guide to an employee trainee in solving work problem he encountered in his work enhance employee commitment?	64	86	10	14	74	100
(ii)	Could an employee working as a subordinate partner with a boss so as to eventually assume the full responsibility of the job promote effective succession and employee commitment?	53	71.62	21	28.38	74	100
(iii)	Could job rotation that is designed to give a broad individual experience through exposure to many different areas of the organization promote employee commitment?	54	72.97	20	27.03	74	100
2	<i>To assess the effect of training- off- the-job on organizational commitment</i>						
(i)	Can train that takes employees outside their organization motivate employees?	54	72.79	20	27.03	74	100
(ii)	Can employees acquire relevant skills through apprenticeship training?	56	75.68	18	24.32	74	100
(iii)	Can off - the – job training programmes in universities enhance employees' knowledge and skill and assure organizational commitment?	48	64.86	26	35.14	74	100
3	<i>To ascertain the decision-making skills required for executive development</i>						
(i)	When an executive is fed with information about a company, and he is asked to react to questions concerning the company, can he learn decision making?	56	75.68	18	24.32	74	100
(ii)	If an executive got information about a company and was asked to identify the problem of the company and proffer solutions, can he learn decision making?	53	71.62	21	28.38	74	100
(iii)	Can an executive learn decision making when he can successfully react to a problem situation?	58	78.38	16	21.62	74	100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Analyses of Results

The responses obtained from the questions asked on the effect of training- on – the – job on employee commitment are 64, 53, and 54 representing 86%, 71.62%, and 72.97% respectively gave answers in the affirmative while 10, 21, and 20 representing 14%, 28.38%, and 27.03% respectively had a contrary opinion.

H₁ Training- on – the – job has positive effect on employee commitment

Table 2: Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) Test Result for Hypothesis (I).

Parameter Estimates

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold [Employee Commitment = 10]	19.203	.021	17.256	1	.008	19.203	19.895
Location [Training_on_the_job =41]	38.406	.075	31.025	1	.000	38.406	38.496

Link function: Logit.

The (OLR) result in table (2) revealed that training-on-the-job had positive effect on employee commitment, with an increase in the odds (probability) of increased commitment at an odds ratio of 38.406 (95% CI, 38.406 to 38.496), Wald $\chi^2(1) = 31.025$, $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.000$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis which states that training on-the-job has a positive effect on employee commitment is hereby accepted, and the null hypothesis rejected.

The responses obtained from the questions asked on the effect of training- off – the- job on organizational commitment are 54, 56, and 48 representing 72.97%, 75.68%, and 64.86% respectively gave answers in the affirmative while 20, 18 and 26 representing 27.03%, 24.32%, and 35.14% respectively had a contrary opinion.

H₂ Training- off – the – job has positive effect on organizational commitment

Table 3: Ordinal Logistic Regression Test Result for Hypothesis (ii)

Parameter Estimates

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold [Organisational-Commitment = 20]	24.290	7.052	20.524	1	.020	24.290	26.290
Location [Training-off-the-job = 44]	39.406	18.250	14.985	1	.000	39.406	40.579

Link function: Logit.

The result in table (3) revealed that training- off-the-job had positive effect on organisational commitment with an increase in the odds (probability) of increased commitment at an odds ratio of 39.406 (95% CI, 39.406 to 40.579), Wald $\chi^2(1) = 14.985$, $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.000$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis which states that training- off-the-job has a positive effect on organizational commitment is hereby accepted, and the null hypothesis rejected.

The responses obtained from the questions asked on the decision-making skills required for executive development are 56, 53, and 58 representing 75.68%, 71.62%, and 78.38% respectively gave answers in the affirmative while 18, 21 and 16 representing 24.32%, 28.38%, and 21.62% respectively had a contrary opinion.

H₃: In–basket–training programme and case studies training programme are decision-making skills required for executive development.

Table 4: Ordinal Logistic Regression Test Result for Hypothesis (iii)

Parameter Estimates

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold [Executive_Development = 18]	14.203	12.000	16.258	1	.022	14.203	15.203
Location [In_basket_training=21]	8.406	7.056	11.565	1	.001	8.406	10.406
Location [Case_studies_training=16]	16.202	14.855	18.925	1	.032	16.202	17.521

Link function: Logit.

The result in the table (4) revealed that in–basket–training programme and case studies training programme were decision-making skills required for executive development. With an increase in the odds (probability) of increased development at an odds ratio of 8.406, 16.202 (95% CI, 8.406 to 10.406 and 16.202 to 17.521), Wald $\chi^2(1) = 11.565$, 18.925; $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.001$, 0.032). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis which states that in –

basket – training programme and case studies training programme are decision-making skills required for executive development is hereby accepted, and the null hypothesis rejected.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The study examined the effect of training on – the – job of employee commitment. The result from the ordinal logistic regression showed that training on- the- job had positive effect on employee commitment ($\beta = 38.406$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$). This indicates that organizational performance and commitment increase when a newly employed person receives guidance and counseling from a superior in the organization and when an employee moves from one job to another in order to have a broad experience. Moreso, when a manager rates employee's performance in accordance with the predetermined performance criteria over a period of time. Meyer and Allen (1997) established that to effectively develop such knowledge, skills and capabilities of employees to perform well, on – the - job training programmes are necessary for supporting the organizational members.

Consequently, the study also examined the effect of training- off – the- job on organizational commitment. The finding revealed that training-off-the-job had positive effect on organizational commitment ($\beta = 39.406$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$). Training- off- the- job involves any form of training that takes place outside the work premises. This implies that the employee does not count as a directly productive worker while such training takes place. Training off- the –job utilizes lectures, case studies, simulation, and executive development programmes at universities or other educational institutions. Training-off – the – job also involves vestibule training and apprenticeship training. Buckley and Caple (2009) see training- off-the-job as a systematic process that aims to help employees enhance their knowledge, skills, and develop positive behavior through a learning experience that is expected to help employees achieve greater performance.

Moreso, the study examined the decision-making skills required for executive development. The result revealed that in–basket–training programme and case studies training programme were decision making skills required for executive development ($\beta = 8.406$, 16.202 , $P = 0.001$, $0.032 < 0.05$). Executive development is relevant as it is needed for the long run success of the organization through the acquisition of job skills, knowledge, insight, and attitudes to effectively manage the organization. Elnaga and Imran (2013) revealed that employee training refers to programmes that aim to provide employees with required information, new skills to enhance the opportunities for professional development. Diab and Ajlouni (2015) established that the main principles of training stand on providing meaningful inputs for employees based on important theories, and to take into account the features of effectiveness and efficiency, differences among employees and continuous development.

CONCLUSION

Employee's knowledge and skills have become essential for organization performance, competitiveness, and innovation. Human resource capital is a basic source to achieve competitive advantage. The flexible structures of some organisations and the nature of management moving towards the devolution of power to the workforce, give increasing emphasis to an environment of coaching and support: Training is necessary to ensure an adequate supply of staff that are technically and socially competent, and capable of career advancement into specialist departments or management positions. On –the job training programmes domiciled and utilized in the university are orientation program designed for fresh workers, workshops, and seminars organized for workers in their workplaces. Off – the – job-training programmes that were also utilized in the university are sabbatical leave, conferences, leave with and without pay which allows an employee to enroll in an educational programme in a university to acquire and update knowledge. There is, therefore, a continual need for the process of staff development, and training fulfills an important part of this process. An employee is motivated when he or she is given the opportunity to acquire and update skills. A motivated worker is satisfied and will be willing to stay with the organization, attends work regularly and protects the company's assets.

RECOMMENDATIONS

These suggestions were lifted in order to secure the full benefits of successful training,

- (i) There should, therefore, be a planned and systematic approach to the effective management of training.
- (ii) There should be a clear commitment to training throughout all levels of the organization. Top management should set the scene by giving active support and encouragement to the training process, and through the provision of adequate finance, resources, time and skilled staff.
- (iii) There should be an objective assessment of training needs related to - a vision of where the organization is going; they need to be responsive to changes in external environmental influences, a comprehensive system of human resource planning, and a process of job analysis leading to the preparation of job descriptions and person specifications.
- (iv) There should be a clear set of objectives and a defined policy for training. The expected results of training should be understood clearly and realistically, and be seen as reasonably attainable.
- (v) Consideration should be given to external courses and training opportunities linked to the educational system. These include programmes designed to provide improved employment opportunities and centered on standards of occupational competence, those which are essentially vocational in nature, and relevant professional, diploma and degree courses.
- (vi) There should be an effective system of review and evaluation including the ongoing monitoring of progress, a supporting appraisal system and the maintenance of suitable training records (Schneider and Barsoux, 2003).
- (vii) Training should be seen as an integral part of total quality management process whereby employees acquire and update skills and knowledge.

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